

Voter Competence and Epistemic Arguments for Democracy

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Abstract

Epistemic democrats argue that democracy is better than other political regimes not only morally, but also epistemically. They claim that, despite well-documented public ignorance, democratic decision-making is epistemically preferable to alternatives: as decision-making mechanisms democratic deliberation and majority vote through free and fair elections outperform decisions by expert bodies. There are several theoretical explanations for why this might be the case. This paper discusses the applicability of Condorcet's Jury Theorem (CJT) and the Diversity Trumps Ability Theorem (DTAT) proved by Lu Hong and Scott E. Page. These two theorems are believed to explain how bigger groups of moderately competent problem solvers outperform smaller groups of individually more competent problem solvers. The analysis of these theorems leads to the conclusion that more inclusive democratic deliberation as well as free fair and periodic democratic elections will hardly satisfy democratic needs or outperform expert bodies. To function epistemically well democracies need to heavily rely on experts. The paper concludes with the conjecture that heavy institutionalization of expertise might be the best way to develop democracies.

Keywords: democracy, knowledge problem, epistemic democrats, experts, Condorcet's jury theorem, diversity trumps ability theorem

Democracy's Knowledge Problem

Democracies are guided by the will of the majority. In democratic systems, fundamental political power is equally distributed among all citizens, who decide where their political community should be headed through free, fair, and periodical elections. Through elections, citizens also judge whether their country is moving toward the democratically identified goals, whether it progresses along an efficient enough path etc.

Thus, the success of democracies depends on the quality of elections. If the public is not informed about political realia, as well as facts from the social and natural sciences, then their decisions may not only fail to serve the best interests of the political community and its individual members, but may also conflict with their preferences. For instance, if the majority of voters are against increasing international debt but are unaware that the incumbent ruling party has increased the country's international debt and plans to borrow more, they might still vote for it. If the general public is not adequately informed, it will fail to choose the best candidates,

define good goals, and supervise government activities. As a result, the public will cause considerable harm to its members, neighboring nations, and future generations—either by initiating harmful projects or by missing opportunities.

Unfortunately for epistemic democrats, the public is ignorant of political realia as well as many relevant scientific facts. This issue is widely recognized and discussed (Goldman, 1999; Achen & Bartels, 2016; Brennan, 2016). Moreover, Anthony Downs' widely accepted explanation of political ignorance suggests that efforts to educate and/or inform the public are unlikely to succeed (Downs, 1957). This is the first face of democracy's knowledge problem: on the one hand, fundamental political power belongs to the people; on the other hand, it appears that if left on their own devices, people are unlikely to arrive at quality decisions on the most pressing problems they face.

Policies built on true scientific accounts of current realia and potential results of proposed government interventions are, unsurprisingly, prone to succeed. So democracies, like any other political regime, require truth-tracking policies and government decisions built on truth. Relying on the best available evidence is both practically advantageous and morally commendable. If the application of some body of knowledge could help society save resources and improve people's well-being, then, *ceteris paribus*, it should be applied. To address the knowledge problem just described, liberal democracies, possibly because of such considerations, have gradually involved more experts in ever-growing domains of decision-making. Today, experts are virtually indispensable for solving pressing social, economic, ecological, medical, and other problems of contemporary complex societies.

Devising the most efficient course for overcoming a recession, developing a new vaccination against diseases like COVID-19, designing a more efficient wind turbine, a safer nuclear fusion reactor, and so forth can be implemented only by expert communities—that is, collectives of highly specialized, thoroughly knowledgeable, and skilled individuals.

Contemporary science holds immense authority. Science is often regarded as a means by which we discover the reality, what is possible and what is impossible, and as a result, politicians play politics and citizens play citizens within a reality defined by scientists. If a disease can be overcome without quarantine, then limiting people's freedom is unwarranted; if there are no winds 60 meters above the ground, building a wind turbine may be pointless, and so on. Thus, whenever there are relevant scientific facts, political power is built upon them. Going against science conspicuously is not a viable option. Thus, even if experts do not hold "formal political control," they may still have substantial influence on society, as their ideas and methods of inquiry have been adopted by governments (Moore, 2017, pp. 38-40).

Virtually all theorists agree that experts must be accountable to the public. Expert power must be limited by and balanced against some democratic procedures. Expert communities should, for instance, be accountable to the public on multiple fronts: how allocated funds are used, whether they abide by relevant laws and regulations, whether they adequately respond to societal challenges in a timely manner, and so on. However, attempts to ensure expert accountability are not only prohibitively expensive due to knowledge asymmetry, but can also be counterproductive, as institutionalized accountability mechanisms may hinder expert work and destroy their intrinsic motivation to produce knowledge (Moore, 2017, p. 48; Herzog, 2023, p. 186).

In order to be productive and to serve the public well, expert communities need to have some independence from direct political and/or economic pressures. This applies to all expert bodies, such as courts, media, universities, central banks, and others. They should be reasonably distanced from political, ideological, and commercial pressures (Moore 2017, pp. 34-35). The content of expert advice should be produced free from political interests and pressures. One way expert communities can serve the public is by keeping an eye on government activities as well as the activities of major economic players. And to be in a position to serve in this way, expert communities must be protected from direct influence of the government and other political actors. Thus, keeping experts accountable is an intricate task.

Some believe that representative democracies can avoid the knowledge problem just described. The literature has put forward a number of views on how this might happen. One suggestion is dividing the cognitive labor: the public should delegate the solution of technical problems to experts while retaining the right to determine societal values, as well as the fundamental political structure and goals of the society. Christiano presents the idea as follows: "...citizens [can be] charged with the task of defining the aims the society is to pursue while legislators [with the help of experts—A.B.] are charged with the tasks of implementing and devising the means to those aims through the making of legislation" (Christiano, 2008, p. 104).

The idea is as follows. Even if people are not informed about political realia and are not knowledgeable in economics, sociology, international relations, biology, physics, and other fields, they might still be able to identify relatively competent and benevolent candidates and vote for them. These elected representatives, with the help of skilled and knowledgeable experts, would then develop and implement policies aimed at achieving the general societal goals set by the public. The public, according to this scheme, would evaluate representatives' work through subsequent elections. By dividing the cognitive labor in this way, democracies, it is believed, will make quality

decisions, thus addressing democracy's knowledge problem.

However, many scholars question whether this value-only voting is a feasible option. If the public is not informed about political realities, why believe they will choose the right candidates? And why believe they will give the right feedback to incumbent politicians through elections? Various authors have also argued that adding intermediaries—especially unelected intermediaries like experts who are supposed to help the elected representatives—between the public and political decisions deprives people of political power and is undemocratic. Experts are not voted for, they are not accountable to people, yet they command massive power. This seems to violate the principle of democratic equality (Moore, 2017, p. 37; Herzog, 2023, p. 177). Delegating decision-making to political representatives and experts alienates people from political power.

This objection from political alienation is not the only argument against expert-enhanced representative democracies. Heavy reliance on experts meets resistance for a number of reasons, including the following:

- a) There is no value-neutral science.
- b) Expert knowledge and decisions not only resolve factual disputes but also moral ones. However, experts in fields such as economics or mining are not moral experts—and perhaps no one is.
- c) It is difficult to identify real experts, especially in political or policy matters (Goldman, 2001; Tetlock, 2005).
- d) Experts sometimes make mistakes; they may be dishonest, ideologically biased, etc. (Holst & Molander, 2019, pp. 545-547).

These observations reveal the second face of democracy's knowledge problem: science is a double-edged sword. On the one hand, societies need it to address various pressing problems; on the other hand, it risks converting democracies into technocracies and/or alienating people from power.

Hence, once again, it appears that either democracies will be well run by knowledgeable and responsible political elites with the help of experts, or they will be democratically legitimate.

Many leading contemporary thinkers acknowledge that if the public is left on its own devices it will be prone to poor decisions; however, they claim that experts are not necessarily a threat to democracy or to the legitimacy of political decisions. Some leading scholars agree that experts are unavoidable if democracies are to function well and that "certain 'epistemic drift' seems inevitable" for a well-functioning democracy (Holst & Molander, 2019, p. 543). Others acknowledge that in certain circumstances "experts are of greatest value to democracy" (Schudson, 2006, p. 491). Experts contribute to democracy by informing public deliberation (Fishkin & Simon, 2002). They can also protect democracies from sliding into pop-

ulism by serving as a mechanism of checks and balances (Collins, Evans, Durant, & Weinel, p. 37).

However, some claim that democracy can function without expert bodies. In the next section, we will discuss two arguments that claim majority voting and deliberation in large groups can produce epistemically good outcomes, despite public ignorance.

Epistemological Arguments for Democracy

Several well-known arguments suggest that democratic decision-making is epistemically superior to alternatives, such as decisions based on expert advice, despite the well-documented public ignorance. Two of the best-known arguments invoke Condorcet's Jury Theorem (CJT) and the Diversity Trumps Ability Theorem (DTAT) (Goldman, 1999; Anderson, 2006; Landmore, 2013). Below, we will discuss their applicability to existing political realia.

Condorcet's Jury Theorem

As discussed above, democracies make decisions through voting. Votes can be viewed as answers to questions such as: Which of the two candidates or policies is the better one? CJT claims that if certain conditions are met, then the larger the number of voters, the higher the probability that the majority vote will be correct. If these conditions—to be outlined shortly—hold, then CJT applies across cultural, religious, economic, and other settings. The conditions CJT requires are as follows:

- a) There are two options to choose from, and one of them is better than the other.
- b) Each voter has a greater than 50 % chance of selecting the better option (i.e., the better candidate and/or policy).
- c) Voters vote independently of each other.
- d) Voters vote sincerely rather than strategically (Landmore, 2013, p. 148).

These requirements, of course, are not always met. First, voters often have to choose among multiple candidates or policies, rather than between two options. Second, voters may select the correct or better option in less than 50 % of cases. This is not only because, as noted above, the public tends to be ignorant about political matters, but also because they may be influenced by misleading propaganda. Third, voters typically discuss candidates and policies before voting, thereby influencing one another. And finally, when there are more than two candidates, voters often engage in strategic voting. Thus, although CJT is mathematically proven, its practical applicability can be questioned.

However, the requirements of CJT are not as demanding as it is often assumed. First, as Landmore (2013) claims, many democratic assemblies in fact “break down their decisions into pairwise votes.” Even if this were not the case, one could argue that such a process could be implemented in theory, and this makes “a binary framework [...] perfectly plausible” (Landmore, 2013, pp. 149-150, see also Goodin & Spiekermann, 2018, pp. 26-31).

Some scholars argue that the public satisfies the second condition as well. After all, CJT requires only that individuals perform better than random chance. Landmore (2013), for instance, claims that since individuals are much more likely than chance to find the correct answer to personal questions, we should assume that they are also capable of making good “public decisions” (p. 152).¹ Others argue that the public may be more competent and knowledgeable than survey results suggest because surveys have elitist biases (Lupia, 2006). Moreover, despite their ignorance, laypersons may still vote competently by relying on cues from their more knowledgeable peers (Goldman, 1999, pp. 318-320; Goodin & Spiekermann, 2018, p. 9).

What about independence? In fact, absolute independence of votes is only an ideal. CJT does not require complete isolation of voters. Even if voters are exposed to the same media sources or are part of the same religious or cultural groups, their votes may still be independent enough for CJT to apply. In a society where there is a genuine plurality of views, free and diverse media, and people vote freely, the correlation between votes may be low enough for CJT to apply (Goodin & Spiekermann, 2018, pp. 68-69).

Do people vote sincerely, strategically or in a self-interested way? The literature on voter psychology suggests that people often vote altruistically rather than egoistically (Popkin, 1994, p. 21). Moreover, when there is a large number of voters, the likelihood that any given vote will be decisive dramatically decreases, thereby lowering the motivation to vote strategically (Landmore, 2013, p. 156). Thus, there are reasons to believe that CJT’s requirement of sincere voting is often satisfied.

This provides reasons to trust the results of free and fair elections in liberal democracies and to resort to voting more frequently and on a broader range of issues. However, CJT clearly cannot be applied to solving technical problems, such as devising the most efficient course for overcoming an economic recession, developing a new vaccination against diseases like COVID-19, and the like. Before voting on such issues, thoroughly competent individuals are needed to propose viable alternatives. Yet de-

¹ This, clearly is a problematic claim. Landmore herself acknowledges one aspect of the problem: personal life and public life are fundamentally different. Individuals are well informed about facts relevant to their personal decisions, but they often lack knowledge relevant to public life.

vising alternatives is not enough; the general public often lacks the expertise required to understand these options and effectively compare their merits. In such cases, the public must rely heavily on expert knowledge.

It is often assumed that policy problems require less specialized knowledge. However, the points mentioned in the preceding paragraph may apply to at least some policy problems. Before people can vote, agendas must first be set and this seems to require a wealth of knowledge and deliberation. Moreover, there may be politically important issues about which the public is extremely poorly informed. If all CJT conditions except the second are met, the majority of a large electorate will almost certainly make the wrong choice. In such cases, the rule of experts might be preferable to majority rule.

Finally, as noted above, when the CJT requirements are satisfied, the majority view is almost certainly correct. Thus, it seems that CJT implies citizens should abstain from all forms of protest after voting takes place. For obvious reasons, this implication appears antidemocratic (Anderson, 2006, p. 12).

Diversity Trumps Ability Theorem

In this section, we will discuss the second argument that epistemic democrats rely on. According to DTAT, under some conditions, “a team of randomly selected agents outperforms a team comprised of the best-performing agents” (Hong & Page, 2004, p. 16385). This theorem claims that if a problem is complex, problem solvers are smart, cognitively diverse, numerous, and selected from an even larger pool, then a group of average problem solvers outperform a small group of individually outstanding problem solvers (Page, 2007). Let us clarify what is meant by each of these four conditions:

- a) A problem is complex if none of the problem solvers consistently finds the best answer.
- b) A problem solver is “smart” if, whenever facing two alternative solutions to the problem, they understand which is the better solution and adopt it.
- c) Problem solvers are cognitively diverse if they have different perspectives (i.e., they view the situation or problem differently from one another) and employ different heuristics (i.e., their cognitive actions, such as inferring causes, finding patterns etc., differ) (Page, 2007). Hong and Page (2004) argue that cognitive diversity contributes to the success of collective problem-solving at least as much as individual ability. If problem solvers are cognitively diverse, the diversity of local optima ensures that the intersection of their individual local optima contains the global optimum.

- d) Finally, DTAT will be applicable only if problem solvers are numerous and the initial pool of potential problem solvers from which they are randomly selected is even larger.

DTAT is expected to work for democracy because the problems democracies face are usually complex. Groups of individually best problem solvers tend to be cognitively homogeneous and thus get stuck at a sub-optimal local optimum. Randomly selected problem solvers, on the other hand, tend to be cognitively diverse and can overcome this. As a result they have a higher chance of reaching the global optimum.

Some authors view DTAT as an important theoretical basis for epistemic democracy. One advantage DTAT has over CJT is that, instead of aggregating individual judgments, it encourages the exchanging reasons for and against a given opinion or problem solution. In other words, it incorporates deliberation (Anderson, 2006).

Political decision-making can be viewed as a form of problem-solving. It is reasonable to assume that, on average, more inclusive groups are more cognitively diverse than less inclusive ones. Based on these two assumptions, and inspired by DTAT's mathematical proof, Landemore (2013) proposes the "Numbers Trump Ability Theorem, according to which, under the right conditions and all things being equal otherwise, what matters most to the collective intelligence of a problem-solving group is not so much individual ability as the number of people in the group" (p. 104). This provides epistemic support for inclusive democratic deliberation.

Is Landemore's optimism warranted? Is DTAT applicable to real societies? And how can it be applied? Many worries about the applicability of the Hong-Page theorem have been raised (Houlou-Garcia, 2017; Brennan, Samarzija, & Cassam, 2023).

Landemore herself acknowledges that, even if a randomly selected group of people sometimes outperforms the group of individually best problem solvers, this outcome is not likely. In general, groups composed of individually smart people solve problems much better than groups of randomly selected people. Applications of DTAT in political life are, at best, limited because it relies on a number of unrealistic assumptions. Hong and Page themselves note two of these:

- a) There are no transaction costs between deliberators. That is, when numerous people share their solutions to a problem or exchange reasons for and against various proposed solutions, they lose no time, energy, or other resources.
- e) People share the same "value function," i.e. they "want to maximize a value function that is assumed to have a unique maximum" (Hong & Page, 2004, p. 16387).

The first assumption is mistaken, because the larger the number of

randomly selected problem solvers, the greater the transaction costs become. For example, the cost of communicating one's solution to all other problem solvers increases as the number of problem solvers grows. Moreover, as Hong and Page themselves note, the more cognitively diverse the problem solvers, the higher the transaction costs (Hong & Page, 2004, pp. 16385-6). Thus, even if greater inclusiveness brings some epistemic benefits by increasing the cognitive diversity of problem solvers, it also introduces costs—most notably, the risk of jamming communication among problem solvers.

As a result, for both practical and epistemic reasons some individuals need to be excluded from deliberation. But how should deliberators be chosen? Should they be randomly selected citizens, elected political representatives, or experts? The answer clearly depends on the nature of the questions to be discussed. If the question is sufficiently technical, deliberators should be relevant experts. Otherwise, randomly selected citizens and/or elected representatives may be involved.

The second assumption is mistaken because not all problem solvers share the same values. For example, some individuals invited to address the problem of transportation in a megacity might focus on ways to enable private car ownership to everyone, while others may prioritize reducing greenhouse gas emissions by promoting public transportation, and so forth.

DTAT's applicability is implausible due to other unrealistic assumptions as well.

It assumes that the general public is smarter than it actually is. As noted above, the theorem presumes that when agents are stuck in a local optimum, they can become unstuck only with the help of another agent who proposes a better solution to the problem. Once this occurs, the stuck agent (and everyone else) accepts the new solution, and the group of problem-solvers progresses. In other words, the theorem assumes the following:

- c) One's solution to a problem is always improved when encountering a better alternative.
- a) One's solution is never replaced by a worse one.

Both of these points, however, are false and for obvious reasons. Claim c) is mistaken because humans often ignore better solutions due to various psychological, political, ideological, and other reasons. Similarly, claim d) is unwarranted, as individuals sometimes their own superior solution to a problem by adopting a peer's flawed solution instead. This seems particularly likely in cases involving policy and/or political issues, which are inherently loaded with ideological, evaluative, and personal interest considerations.

When it comes to technical problems such as those listed above,

DTAT's condition b) becomes implausible. The general public is not competent enough to distinguish a better chemical formula for a vaccine from a worse one, or to evaluate the effectiveness of different turbine designs. Therefore, even if the approach favored by DTAT can be applied to certain policy issues, it remains inapplicable to many problems contemporary societies face. There is no reason to expect that the average citizen can assess the comparative advantages of two proposed fiscal policies and consistently select the better one. Nor should it be expected that the public can reliably identify superior standards for fortifying wheat with folic acid, among other matters. The general public lacks the necessary expertise to render DTAT a viable alternative to reliance on expert bodies.

Of course, involving individuals from all segments of society in deliberations is not only morally and politically commendable, but may also bring epistemic benefits by helping policymakers identify such issues which could otherwise stay unnoticed. For example, it can help policymakers identify issues affecting small groups, or uncover burdens that a newly proposed policy imposes on inhabitants of a particular region. However, most policies are—and ideally should be—built on detailed and robust economic, sociological, engineering, and other theories, models, and calculations. The general public, cognitively diverse as it may be, lacks the adequate cognitive resources required to comprehend these complexities. This limits their capacity to participate meaningfully in relevant problem-solving processes.

This discussion suggests that two of the most promising arguments for justifying the general public's ability to function without experts are unsatisfactory. The next section explores approaches for integrating experts and expert knowledge into democratic societies.

Institutionalization of Expertise

What, then, do we have before us? Democracies, on the one hand, must base their policies and decisions on scientific evidence and expert knowledge. On the other hand, they must be guided by the will of the majority who, as empirical findings confirm, are ignorant. CJT and DTAT do not guarantee that majority voting or public deliberation will lead to satisfactory outcomes. Rather, they demonstrate that under certain institutional arrangements, established practices, and conditions, majority votes and democratic deliberation can produce desirable results. Both CJT and DTAT presuppose that citizens are minimally well-informed and competent. CJT requires citizens to be competent enough to choose the correct option with a probability higher than 50 %, while DTAT assumes that citizens are capable of selecting the better of two proposed solutions to a given problem. Clearly, these requirements are not always satisfied. Therefore, in or-

der to succeed, democracies must rely on experts.

As noted above, science and expertise are double-edged swords. Democracies need them to ensure efficiency and to avoid populism, yet they also create the risk of transforming democracies into technocracies. To benefit from available knowledge while mitigating this risk, contemporary democracies have established numerous expert bodies, such as supreme courts, central banks, regulatory and audit agencies, advisory committees, and universities, that are distanced from political and commercial pressures. What else can democracies do?

The optimal relation between democratic societies and expert communities requires a range of institutions (e.g. legal framework) and individual values that bring forth relevant social practices. For a society to epistemically well-functioning, it must ensure freedom of speech, a free and independent media, autonomous think tanks, and universities. In addition to these and many other institutions, epistemically well-functioning democracies also require epistemically responsible individuals who, for instance, refrain from spreading misinformation, contribute to the establishment of epistemic justice, and so forth.

Existing democracies are diverse. Some have highly developed democratic institutions, while others do not. Some have strong expert communities, while others do not. In some democracies, expert advice mechanisms are institutionalized, while in others they are not, etc.² Specific recommendations for further improving the functional relationship between societies and expert communities can be developed only after substantial empirical investigation of conditions within each particular democracy. However, further institutionalization of expertise with radical enhancement of expert accountability mechanisms appears to be a recommendation that all democracies can embrace.

Electoral and liberal democracies can benefit from both instituting more expert bodies and, at the same time, radically enhancing the transparency of expert involvement in public decision-making. Most, if not all, contemporary democracies have laws and regulations specifying when and how expert probation for given large-scale projects must be carried out. For example, Environmental Impact Assessment are typically required before a mining site is exploited, or, before a drug is registered, it must

² It is worth noting that, according to democracy indexes, highly developed democracies tend to have higher knowledge capital. According to one ranking, the five strongest democracies in the world are Denmark, Norway, Finland, Sweden, and Germany. See (Lauth & Lemm, 2022). These countries rank 6th, 1st, 5th, 4th, and 14th, respectively, in the Economist Intelligence Unit ranking (Economist Intelligence Unit, 2023, p. 7). These same countries also score highly in terms of reliance on expertise. According to the UNDP and MBRF Global Knowledge Index, they occupy the 7th, 9th, 4th, 2nd, and 13th positions, respectively (UNDP, MBRE, & Al Ghurair, 2021, p. 5) Similarly, the WIPO Global Innovation Index places them at the 9th, 20th, 7th, 2nd, and 10th, respectively (WIPO; Dutta, Lanvin, Rivera Leon, & Wunsch-Vincent, 2021, p. 4). According to these rankings, weak democracies and weak expert communities are also correlated. These correlations suggest that experts do not harm democracies, but rather strengthen them.

undergo multiple stages of expert review, etc. The proposal here is to expand the scope of public initiatives that require the approval of relevant expert bodies before they can be implemented by governments, funded, or even licensed. Governments could enhance expert involvement in two ways. First, they could solicit independent expert advice for initiatives that currently receive approval only from bureaucrats or government-hired experts. Second, they could also demand much more comprehensive and in-depth evaluation of projects that currently undergo some form of expert review.

Obviously, governments cannot conduct thorough research on all aspects of society and for all initiatives. Quality expert advice is costly, and at one point, additional research will incur more costs than benefits. Governments need to choose wisely and democratically. Priority might be given either to initiatives that are potentially the most dangerous, or to projects that are particularly expensive or that can influence a large portion of the population. For example, governments could decide to hire experts to evaluate a particular project if it costs more than, say 0.5 % of the annual budget, or directly affects the interests of, over, for instance, 5 % of the population.

Further expert input in policies through institutionalization of expertise should be paired with a radical enhancement of decision-making transparency. The entire process of involving experts in decision-making should be institutionalized. Many democracies already have guidelines and principles regarding how expert advice should be solicited, for what types of issues, how expert bodies should operate, and how they should communicate their findings (OECD, 2015, p. 5).

Virtually all democracies already have accountability and transparency policies in place. They publish reports about their activities and results achieved, organize public hearings, have freedom of information laws, among other measures. However, it can be argued that all governments could further improve their transparency and accountability policies by:

- a) Justifying their expert choices—Why was a given expert hired for a specific task? If no expert was hired, why not?
- f) Publishing the raw data collected by governments and the expert bodies they employ.
- g) Publishing the advice given by expert bodies on which government decisions were based.
- h) Disclosing alternative solutions to the given problem that both the hired experts and the government considered.

Further institutionalization of expertise, paired with the radical enhancement of transparency in the entire expert advice process, will make expert opinions readily available to the public, civil society, independent

experts, as well as decision-makers. There are multiple epistemic benefits that may stem from greater transparency of expert advisory processes. First and foremost, it will enable all interested parties to question and probe the expert opinion governments receive. Transparency will contribute to expert advice being properly interpreted and explained to both governments and laypersons. It will also enable the public to gauge the extent to which governments abide by expert advice.

Second, transparency will also prevent experts from aligning too closely with power elites. If the entire process of expert advising, as well as the underlying research, is meticulously recorded and published, the general public will be able to detect illicit inferences and potential collusion with power elites (Holst & Molander, 2019, pp. 550-555). This will help hold experts accountable and ultimately shield them from political pressures. Ensuring the accountability of expert communities benefits not only the public, but also expert communities themselves: it protects them from complacency and corruption.

Third, radical transparency will contribute to the development of trust in experts. Transparency will also contribute to the development of trust toward experts. If the whole cycle of knowledge generation and application is easily trackable, independent experts will be able to review the work of experts hired by governments and thus either improve it or enhance its credibility by reaffirming results (Holst & Molander, 2019, p. 556). As a result, it might help societies overcome the above-mentioned worries about reliance on experts. For example, it will facilitate the discovery of genuine experts, as well as the identification of value judgements intertwined with experts' scientific opinions.

Fourth, transparency also has the potential to contribute to the democratization of policy-related research. Laypersons can be involved in the knowledge production process by contributing to the selection of problems to be studied, as well as to discussions about the thresholds of justifiedness of various claims supporting a given policy.

The radical enhancement of transparency will contribute to further democratization of knowledge and to efficient two-way communication between expert communities and the general public. However, efficient communication requires not only transparency in government advice, but also a number of other institutions, practices, and values that guide individual and collective choices and actions. Media, public hearings, educational institutions, and so forth, are some of the important communication channels. Both expert communities and the society as a whole are responsible for creating and maintaining these reliable mechanisms for their partnership. Experts must proactively communicate socially, politically, economically, and other forms of important knowledge to the general public on a timely basis, and remain open-minded and willing to

learn from the general public about its values and the issues it faces. The general public must support the establishment of truthful, non-partisan, and responsible media that discourages polarization of the public, helps the public discover genuine experts, and accurately assess the extent of agreement among them (Herzog, 2023, pp. 198-203).

Conclusion

Democratic legitimacy is in conflict with knowledge in general, and scientific knowledge in particular. Democracies, including constitutional liberal democracies, require that countries be guided by the majority's will. But as contemporary societies are extremely complex and face complex technical and political challenges, pure majority rule is hardly sustainable for contemporary liberal constitutional democracies.

Recently, epistemic democrats have expressed high hopes of demonstrating the opposite by invoking Condorcet's Jury Theorem and the Diversity Trumps Ability theorem. The discussion above suggests, however, that these do not provide sufficient grounds to believe that pure majority votes and/or large-scale inclusive public deliberation will produce epistemically adequate solutions to pressing technical and political issues.

This paper concludes that experts are indispensable for democracies—and will likely remain so in the foreseeable future. Rather than seeking to restore political freedom by limiting expert authority, democracies should, on the one hand, expand the extent to which government decisions are informed by expert advice and, on the other hand, radically enhance the transparency of expert advisory mechanisms.

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